

Contributions and Challenges of Resort Owners in Camarines Norte: Basis for Promotion and Management Plan

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Abstract:- The overarching aimed to unveil the contributions and challenges of resorts owners in Camarines Norte. Specifically, it described the demographic profile of the resort owners in Camarines Norte. In addition, it sought to identify if there a significant relationship between the profile and the contributions of resort operations as well as the profile resort owners and the challenges they encountered. The study utilized the descriptive-correlational method with a survey questionnaire which served as the main tool in data gathering. There are a total of 21 resort owners in the province which comprised the respondents of the study. Based on the data gathered, resort owners in Camarines Norte strongly agree that they contribute to the economic aspects of the province. The study also revealed the challenges encountered by resort owners in their operation in terms of their marketing which they considered moderate problem. Significant relationship between the profile and the challenges of the resort owners encountered in resort operations showed a statistically significant moderate positive relationship at between civil status profile and perceived challenges of the resort owners.

Keywords:- Resort owners, operations management, human resource management, marketing, challenges.

I. INTRODUCTION

Having a stable business in these trying times is a must. In these hard times, having a stable business is necessary. This is done to protect the company's reputation as well as to help employees and their families survive. The pandemic has created far too many problems in the world. Nothing was spared the wrath it wreaked on the business sector. The implementation of community quarantine has had a negative impact on the business sector and all those associated with it. On a brighter note, resorts, which are often privatized by occupants to keep their company safe, have been a hit for those who still wish to enjoy and rest after a long and stressful workday.

According to the 2018 World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) Power and Performance Report, the Philippines ranks 13th among the top 15 tourism powerhouses that had absolute growth over the last seven years. The report, which evaluated 185 countries based on their travel and tourism sector's performance from 2011 to 2017, also ranked the country 15th in terms of performance or compound annual growth rates in WTTC's four

indicators: contribution to GDP, international visitor spending, domestic spend, and capital investment. With a USD66.3 billion contribution to GDP in 2017, the Philippines ranks 8th among governments that have had the greatest development in travel and tourism's contribution to GDP from 2011 to 2017. (NPC, 2018).

In the country's perspective in terms of tourism, according to the Philippine Daily Inquirer (2017), given the archipelagic nature of the Philippines, tourism was identified early on as a low-hanging fruit with great potential to boost the economy. All that was needed, it was believed, was to build roads to provide contact to the country's pristine beaches and other destinations and prod the private sector to put up hotels and other infrastructure to offer to the tourist.

The Republic Act. No. 9593, otherwise known as The Tourism Act of 2009, it declares tourism as an indispensable element of the national economy and an industry of national interest and importance, which must be harnessed as an engine of socio-economic growth and cultural affirmation to generate investment, foreign exchange, and employment, and to continue to mold an enhanced sense of national pride for all Filipinos (Department of Tourism, 2020).

The province of Camarines Norte is divided into twelve (12) municipalities named Basud, Capalonga, Daet (capital), Jose Panganiban, Labo, Mercedes, Paracale, San Lorenzo Ruiz, San Vicente, Sta Elena, Talisay, and Vinzons. The province covers a total area of 2,320.07 square kilometers. The province is surrounded by large bodies of water namely the Lamon Bay, the San Miguel Bay, and the Philippine Sea facing the Pacific east of the province. Camarines Norte province is home to many type of businesses and the majority of which revolves around agriculture and aquaculture. Along with agriculture, tourism is also one of the big magnets of Camarines Norte being mostly covered with beaches and dotted with many islands (BalinkBayan, n.d.).

The resort owners made a profit in 2020, but this does not guarantee that tourism will make the same profit in the future. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic can have a variety of consequences for resort operators. The COVID-19 pandemic has caused commercial downturns and a financial crisis. The World Travel and Tourism Council warned that the COVID-19 pandemic could result in the loss of millions of jobs in the travel and tourism industry, as

travel is predicted to decline dramatically worldwide in 2020. (DUNC, n.d.).

At present, resorts in the province were facing various concerns, such as employment tenure of their employees, income generation or other possible revenue streams from their operations, and worst, the restrictions implemented by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) mandating regulations affecting the operations of these farm resorts, to name a few. It is hard on their part to partially lay-off some employees knowing that these employees also have families to feed and living maintenance expenses to shoulder. They were not receiving enough help from government and other agencies affecting their employees and their establishment just to cope with the vast and pressing COVID 19 situations.

On that point, the province of Camarines Norte went through the same anguish as the rest of the country. Some were forced to close their businesses, while others attempted to expand into the tourism sector. Until recently, resorts were a source of enjoyment for many people and a lucrative commercial opportunity for those who owned land that had been converted into one. Because of various situations, there are both obstacles and possibilities for resort owners. As a result, this necessitates in-depth investigation, which the researcher shed light on.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The main objective of this study was to unveil the contributions and challenges of resort owners in Camarines Norte. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

A. *What is the profile of the resort owners in Camarines Norte in terms of:*

- age;
- civil status;
- educational background;
- number of employees; and
- number of years in business?

B. *What are the contributions of resort owners in terms of:*

- economic;
- environmental; and
- social aspects?

C. *Is there a significant relationship between the profile and the contributions of resort owners?*

D. *What are the main challenges of resort owners encountered in resort operations in terms of:*

- Marketing;
- Operations management; and
- Human resource management?

E. *Is there a significant relationship between the profile and the challenges of resort owners encountered in resort operations?*

F. *What promotion and management plan may be proposed to strengthen the resort operations in the province of Camarines Norte?*

III. SCOPE AND LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The study was limited to the contributions and challenges of resort owners. The respondents were the resort owners in the province of Camarines Norte that provides sleeping accommodations, food, beverage, swimming pools and other recreational facilities. The resorts that are existing below one year was not included in the study.

IV. REVIEW OF LITERATURES

Resorts are said to be one of the main factors attracting tourists, which stimulates economic activity by generating revenue for the area. The resorts' positive impact on employment and growth was also noticeable. They had been dealing with a variety of issues that had hampered their progress up to this point. This research shed more light on the experiences of these resort owners in Camarines Norte. To be more specific, this chapter covers international and local literature on the issues confronting resort owners, which undoubtedly provided ideas and insights for the development of this study.

The resort industry is a branch of the hospitality industry that focuses on providing customers with recreational activities and accommodation. It contributes significantly to the economies of several nations around the world in a variety of ways.

According to the World Tourism Organization (2021), tourism today accounts for one in every eleven new jobs and is one of the main drivers of worldwide economic growth. Society, especially women and young people, can gain from better skills and professional development by providing access to decent employment possibilities in the tourism sector.

Kubickova and Martin (2019), who made the case that tourism has developed into a crucial tool for economic growth and employment creation, exhibiting market competitiveness, lend credence to this. The market is competitive, as tourism has emerged as a key driver of economic expansion and job creation. Tourist destinations must generate new products, markets, and customers while learning how to think more like businesses. Government also plays important roles in the growth of the tourism industry, varying in their amount of involvement.

Tourism is a prominent industry with the capability to generate income for developed as well as developing countries. However, research is still limited, particularly those that focus primarily on how locals see tourists. The perception of the residents is crucial since it could decide how much support they would give to the development of tourism (Afthanorhan et al., 2017).

In recent years, the effects of tourism on the environment have drawn more and more attention. Tourists and stakeholders alike are now recognizing the importance of environmental management in the tourism industry with the rise of sustainable tourism and an increase in environmentally friendly initiatives. Tourism has the potential to have a positive impact on the environment by

helping to protect and conserve the environment. It serves as a means of promoting environmental values and can be used to help pay for the preservation of natural places and boost their economic significance (Stainton, 2021).

Additionally, potential planning is necessary in various marketing strategies and techniques, according to Srisangkaew (2017), to deal with changing customer patterns and demand, which have become more complex. The primary goals of the promotion methods are to increase consumer awareness and spark interest in the target market. The requirement for training service provider workers in the qualities of hospitality, service recovery, communication, and exceeding customers' expectations is evident. Potential clients may find the packaging and programming to be comprehensive and valuable.

Like other commercial organizations, resorts have numerous difficulties. They are sensitive areas since the majority of tourists visit them for leisure and relaxation, which make them more susceptible to even small changes. Since there are numerous resorts to select from, people in charge of running them must uphold high standards to draw customers. The standards are decided, among other things, by interactions between staff and customers, service security, and service affordability (IvyPanda, 2019).

As a tropical country, Philippines is the home of some of the world's finest resorts and classified as a top tourism destination. According to (Landman, 2020), a resort is a full-service accommodation facility that is primarily designed for vacationers and is typically found in locations that are popular for leisure activities, such as beaches, seashores, picturesque or historic sites, ski parks, and spas. The variety of services and amenities provided sets an upscale hotel apart from a basic hotel. A resort is a self-contained facility that accommodates most of a traveler's needs while also maintaining them on the grounds such as lodging, food, drink, sports, entertainment, shopping, among others.

Over the past twenty years, integrated resort construction has flourished. Local business owners start to offer facilities and services after seeing the potential for economic growth. Future tourism policy should be envisioned as a development approach that, while utilizing local resources, controls and plans them carefully to ensure that they are preserved for both current residents and visitors as well as for future generations. (Andriotis, 2019).

Integrated resorts have been viewed as a tool for private investors to increase their profits. Three perspectives—eco-techniques, environmental sponsorship, and eco-packaging—are used to evaluate the strategies used by the global resort business to achieve higher environmental sensitivity and sustainability. It stressed that the financial and environmental arguments for a green hotel fell short of realizing all of a green resort's potentials (Ayala, 2016).

The Department of Tourism is the main branch of the Philippine government in charge of promoting the advantages of tourism to both the public and private sectors, as well as marketing, encouraging, and developing it as a significant socioeconomic activity to provide foreign exchange and employment. The government is not established to incorporate tourism requirements into governance at all levels, claims Libosada (2018) on CNN Philippines. A determined local government representative with vision and tenacity would be required to push for a clearly defined and regulated tourism economy.

Other obstacles to the establishment of the resort industry include a significant image issue and rising rivalry from other sectors. Graft and corruption were the main issues that businesses in the Philippines were facing, followed by an ineffective judicial system, limited business ownership, regulatory systems, the Value-Added Tax (VAT), infrastructure, internet penetration, a market that was extremely price-sensitive, Philippine Government procurement, customs, and tariffs (export.gov., 2019).

A crucial business function, like hospitality operations management, which aims to successfully coordinate the design, development, and delivery of service experiences, is required to deliver experiences in any of these sectors. It entails all the actions, choices, and accountability necessary to successfully run a corporation while utilizing corporate assets. These resources include people, machinery, technology, and even clients. For hotel businesses, effective operations management may really make a difference (Dalton and Yoo, 2021).

Lastly, the hotel industry's human resources have struggled with issues like poor pay, excessive turnover, and the difficulty in finding qualified workers. Employees are the biggest cost for any company, but the hotel industry is particularly affected. One of the few industries where customer happiness has a significant impact on business is the hospitality industry. Employees in the hospitality industry serve as the company's face and promote its values. If hospitality employees are not satisfied, they cannot provide the kind of client service that encourages repeat business. If consumers are not satisfied, the viability of hospitality firms is put in jeopardy (APS Payroll, 2021).

The development of market-oriented worldwide marketing plans is essential for a destination country's tourism economy and enhancing destination competitiveness in the long run as the tourism sector continues to expand despite the current hurdles. A promotion plan that concentrates on one or more target segments of a larger pool of tourism source markets will be beneficial for the development of the tourism industry (Lin et al., 2019).

Gomez et al. (2021) on their study entitled "Sustainable Tourism Development and Economic Growth: Bibliometric Review and Analysis", stressed that sustainable tourism development and economic growth is increasing and maturing. However, considering the dearth of influential articles, there is still a significant gap. This study's evidence points to the necessity of sustainable tourist development for economic expansion. It was suggested that actions to encourage the expansion of sustainable tourism be looked at in order to boost the economy's growth, which is currently being hindered by the pandemic.

On the other hand, Ciangă and Sorocovschi (2017) on their study entitled "The Impact of Tourism Activities: A Point of View", discussed that tourism participates in the sustainable development of numerous destinations by increasing viability of localities with scarce natural resources; use of low productive agricultural land through the implementation of appropriate tourist facilities; increasing cash income of residents; increasing economic power of localities by obtaining new revenue from new taxes and local fees; encouraging, even reviving traditional activities, particularly those with hand-made character and from small-scale traditional industry, but also from traditional ecological mountain farming and through the capitalization of products in city-place; development of a particular trade based on local handicraft products; upgrading cultural objectives and ecological rehabilitating of valued landscapes based on revenues from tourism.

Similarly, Appah (2018) stressed that tourism intangibles like infrastructure development and cultural mix, which give people the chance to experience other cultures, have almost turned into a curse due to the gradual loss of their culture in the study about "Assessing the Impact of Coastal Resort Tourism on Tourism Participation Among the Locals in Hopkins Village, Belize." The study's findings showed how much Hopkins' residents rely on the resorts for their financial security. The majority of participants, on the other side, also discussed how tourism had positively impacted their culture and way of life. Additionally, they band together and collaborate, assisting and empowering the village council to carry out its duties.

On one end, Gonzales (2021) found in her study titled "The Impact of Beach Resorts to Community: Basis for a Community Awareness Program" that one of the most efficient ways to promote economic growth and job creation in local communities is through tourism. The industry improves access to necessary services including water, sanitation, telecommunications, and transportation in addition to helping to create income. The advantages of tourism, however, could potentially be missed by locals if improperly managed. Results showed that respondents benefited greatly from social effects as well as from economic and environmental effects. However, there were issues that were viewed as severe due to the various benefits that beach resort owners and occupants had access to.

Similar to this focus on sustainability in tourism, Quevedo et al study from 2021, "Linking Blue Carbon Ecosystems with Sustainable Tourism: Dichotomy of

Urban-Rural Local Perspectives from the Philippines," shows a clear distinction between urban and rural perceptions. For example, residents in Coron rated tourism's advantages and effects highly, while Busuanga residents gave it less credit. Positive correlations between villagers' perceptions of environmental changes brought on by tourism and their knowledge of Blue Carbon Ecosystems' (BCE) services were found. Plans relating to the environment have been highly praised for fostering sustainable travel. Locals' opinions on tourism and blue carbon ecosystems can be grouped together as a whole.

It is crucial to comprehend the social effects of tourism development on the local community, according to Yu's (2020) paper "Paraisong Nawala: Exploring Sustainable Ecotourism in the Philippines: Environmental Studies Commons." The Philippines can ensure that the members of the population most impacted by ecotourism are able to find stability by encouraging locals to contribute their talents and abilities to the business. Economic opportunity is unavoidably going to be the driving force behind ecotourism.

However, Velos et al. (2020) found that Local Government Units (LGUs) must have a forecast on knowledge of tourist flow in order to plan out their budget focused on the local development of tourism areas. Their study was titled "A Seasonal Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average (Sarima) Model to Forecasting Tourist Arrival in The Philippines: A Case Study in Moalboal, Cebu (Philippines)". The difficulty for tourism destinations is to adapt to this constantly changing environment. The municipality was deemed to lack the plans and methods necessary to facilitate the allocation process, and as a result, it may not be able to optimize its revenue from tourism.

Similar research by Karabulut et al. (2020) on their study "How Pandemic Affect Tourism: International Evidence" indicated that inadequate facilities and a lack of openness in low-income economies are two factors causing a decline in tourism demand. In order to protect the lodging experience of the customers, strict adherence to hygiene and precautionary measures is necessary. This includes complete disinfection, control of food safety, distribution of masks, online medical consultation, health detection of customers and employees, and the closure of laundry rooms, gyms, and other public area facilities. Additionally, they discovered that the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita is positively associated with tourist arrivals in all estimations when compared to the control variables. Tourist arrivals rise in response to an increase in GDP per capita. Arrivals of tourists are positively impacted by the exchange rate.

Lastly, Zenker and Kock (2020) explain in their paper "The Coronavirus Pandemic: A Critical Discussion of a Tourist Research Agenda" that the tourism industry will need to coordinate cooperative efforts and social bricolage during this catastrophe. Promoting agritourism and medical tourism are worthwhile initiatives that developing nations like the Philippines may pursue to aid in the reconstruction of their tourism industries. This pandemic highlights the necessity of understanding tourism within the larger global

economic and political framework that will shape the environment in which it will operate in the future.

V. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The conceptual framework of this study is based on the basic system concept which covers dependent and independent variables.

The identified independent variables included in the study are the profile of the resort owners, contribution of resort owners, and challenges they are facing. In this study, the independent variables considered are the profile of resort owners in the province of Camarines Norte such as age, civil status, educational background, number of employees, and the number of years in business.

Another independent variable considered was the contributions of resort owners particularly on the economic, environmental, and social aspects. The last independent variable was the challenges of these owners in terms of the marketing, operations management and human resource management of the resorts.

The process consists of data gathering through survey questionnaires, interviews, data presentation, analysis and interpretation of data. It is relevant in this study to describe the profile of the resort owners and determine their valuable contributions and challenges encountered. The significant relationship between the profile and their contributions was also analyzed as well as the relationship between profiles and the challenges of the resort owners. Based on the results, an output which is the dependent variable was created is the tourism promotion and management plan for resort owners in the province of Camarines Norte.

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework

VI. METHODOLOGY

A. Method of Research

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational method. It is descriptive because it described the profile of the respondents in terms of age, number of employees, and number of years in business. On the other hand, Somer's Delta Correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between the profile and their contributions as well as the relationship between profile and the challenges of resort owners. Lastly, after the thorough analysis of the data gathered, a proposed promotion and management plan was crafted to boost tourism development in the province of Camarines Norte.

B. Population, Sampling size and Sampling technique

This study utilized duly accredited resorts in the province of Camarines Norte as respondents which have been operating for at least one year at the time of the study. The respondents were twenty-five (25) resort owners who are venturing in the business for more than one year. However, four (4) resort owners firmly declined to participate in the data gathering, which resulted to 21 resort owners in total. These total respondents composed of the registered resorts owners were based on the records of the Provincial Tourism Office, Provincial Government of Camarines Norte in 2021. The study used total enumeration in determining the respondents.

C. Description of Respondents

The resort owners in Camarines Norte were the respondents of the study. The respondents were based on the data provided by the Provincial Tourism Office of Camarines Norte in 2021. Twenty-one (21) resort owners were the total respondents. They were qualified as respondents since they are already venturing in the business for a year or more and are duly registered.

D. Research Instruments

A survey questionnaire was used as the main research instrument for data collection. The questionnaire consisted of three parts to answer the objectives of the study. Cronbach’s alpha coefficient 0.899 indicates a good internal consistency within the items of contributions of resort owners in the questionnaire and Cronbach’s alpha coefficient 0.962 indicates an excellent internal consistency within the items of main challenges encountered by resort owners in the questionnaire. After passing the reliability test, the questionnaire was administered to the intended respondents of the study.

E. Data Gathering Procedure

Data collection began with the acquisition of appropriate documents from relevant offices, such as the Provincial Tourism Office of Camarines Norte, for the purpose of compiling an official list of certified and registered resort owners in the province in 2021. The list of registered resorts in Camarines Norte was requested in writing to the provincial tourism officer.

F. Statistical Treatment

Frequency count and percentage technique were used to evaluate the profile of the respondents such as age, number of employees, number of years in business and highest educational background.

Weighted mean was used to determine the contributions of resort owners on the economic, environmental, and social aspects together with the challenges in resort operations particularly in terms of marketing, operations management and human resource management.

Rank Biserial Correlation and Somer’s Delta Correlation Coefficient were used to determine the significant relationship between the profile and their contributions as well as the relationship between profile and the challenges of the resort owners.

VII. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This part summarizes the conclusions from the study's analysis of the contributions and challenges encountered by resort owners in Camarines Norte, which served as the foundation for a promotion and management strategy that was later developed. This chapter also outlines the results of the rigorous data collection and variation statistics-based analysis of quantitative data.

A. Profile of Respondents

Age. Table 1 shows the breakdown of percentage of the profile of the resort owners in Camarines Norte in terms of age. The age bracket of 35 to 44 has the highest percentage of 23.8 percent with frequency of five. This is followed by the age brackets 45-54, 55-64, and 65 and above, respectively, which has 19 percent with a frequency of four. The age bracket of 35-34, on the other hand, has 14.3 percent or three respondents. Also as shown on the table, the youngest age bracket on the table which is 24 and below has the lowest percentage of 4.8 which is equivalent to one respondent. Moreover, this table is showing that as early as mid-30s, these resort owners were already venturing in the business for a year or more.

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
24 and below	1	4.8
25-34	3	14.3
35-44	5	23.8
45-54	4	19.0
55-64	4	19.0
65 and above	4	19.0
Total	21	100.0

The table above implies that some of the resort owners are ages 35 to 44 years old. They are young adults who have invested in resorts as it continuously grew even after the pandemic. Based on the interviews conducted, these resort owners ventured on this type of business by maximizing their properties that are in strategic locations and developed it to attract customers who are looking for new place to spend their free time and relax.

This is similar in the study of Tubog and Tayco (2017), which revealed that they are mostly aged 31 years and above which could better explain that they are already in the stage of mature adulthood, which makes them capable of running a resort.

Civil Status. Table 2 shows the civil status of the respondents. Majority of the respondents comprising of 14 which is equivalent to 66.7 percent were married. This is followed by the single respondents with a total of five which is equivalent to 23.8 percent. Lastly, the widowed respondents were two or equivalent to 9.5 percent.

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Single	5	23.8
Married	14	66.7
Widowed	2	9.5
Total	21	100.0

It is clear from the table that married respondents made up the majority of the population. This conclusion is reinforced by Table 1, which shows that some of the resort owners are between the ages of 35 and 44. According to the conducted interview, the majority of resort owners are couples or husband and wife, indicating that they manage their resort business and are in charge of its day-to-day operations directly. By doing this, they can easily keep an eye on the company's flawless operations even when one of them is not present.

The findings are almost similar to the study in which majority or 63 or 64.3 percent of the owners/managers were

married. Both business and married couple are about partnerships. There will be conflict or disagreement, but both parties can negotiate and compromise if necessary (Banez, 2019).

Educational Attainment. Table 3 shows the highest educational attainment of the respondents. Majority of which are college graduates with 15 and equivalent to 71.4 percent, followed by college level which yielded 14.3 percent with three respondents. Lastly, the frequency of one for elementary level, masteral units, and doctoral diploma, respectively, with 4.8 percent.

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Elementary level	1	4.8
College Level	3	14.3
College Graduate	15	71.4
Masteral (units)	1	4.8
Doctoral (diploma)	1	4.8
Total	21	100.0

Majority of the respondents are college degree holders. Based on the data above, it can be observed that resort owners that are college graduates have the opportunities to generate income and maximize their wealth that they can use in their resort business. The pursuit of higher education also equips the resort owners to master complex challenges and overcome adversity, contributing to increased happiness and reduced stress. Resort owners who are college graduates are also more likely to be involved in their communities. A bachelor's degree holder contributes to a stronger, more engaged community to provide opportunities for future generations.

It was similar to the study of Consigny et al. (2019) in which the great majority, 11 or 78.6 percent of the owners/managers are college graduates, and this implies that it needs competent knowledge and skills to run a resort.

Number of Employees. Table 4 shows the profile of the resorts in terms of the number of employees. It is evident that most of the resorts has 10 and below number of employees, with 19 having an equivalent of 90.5 percent. This is followed by both 21 to 30 and 30 to 40 employees with one respondent each with a 4.8 percentage.

Number of Employees	Frequency	Percentage (%)
10 and below	19	90.5
21-30	1	4.8
31-40	1	4.8
Total	21	100.0

Table 4 shows that most of the resorts has been operating with only minimal employee, specifically ten employees and below. This is due to the resorts' limited capacity and the fact that the majority of them have been open for little more than five years, which only necessitates a limited staff of resort attendants. They made the decision to hire fewer people because the industry's demand is primarily seasonal or peaks during the summer, holidays, and hot weather. Additionally, because they are hands-on, the owners—who are typically husband and wife teams—assist in running the company and carry out jobs that they are qualified to undertake.

It is somewhat parallel to the study wherein as they operate a small business, the employees range from three employees to 17 employees (Mustapha et al., 2020).

Number of Years in Business. Table 5 shows the profile of the respondents in term of their number of years in business. As shown, the highest frequency is ten with 47.6 percent of the total population of the respondents. This is followed by 6 to 10 years and 11 to 15 years in the business, both with 23.8 percent, making them the second highest result. Lastly is 16 to 20 years in business, the sole resort operating for that range yields a 4.8 percentage.

Number of Years in Business	Frequency	Percentage (%)
5 and below	10	47.6
6-10	5	23.8
11-15	5	23.8
16-20	1	4.8
Total	21	100.0

Table 5 shows that the resorts are in operations for five years and below. Evidently, it shows that there are many resorts who were new in the business. It implies that during the last five years more resort businesses had opened. It indicates that many local business owners have recognized the opportunity presented by the changing culture, in which more and more people are spending time relaxing and resorts are the top destinations. Even local tourists are visiting their own tourist attractions as a way to connect and explore. These enable the resort operations to continue even if a pandemic occurs and things return to normal.

B. Contribution of Resort Owners in Terms of Economic, Environmental and Social Aspects

Economic Aspects. Table 6 shows the contributions of resort owners in terms of economic aspects. The table shows that majority of the respondents strongly agree that resort business promotes local tourism and attract more tourists (local and foreign) to visit the area with a weighted mean of 4.81. It was followed by venturing into resort business greatly contributes to the government thru the tax payment generated by this industry with 4.71 weighted mean. The table also shows the least is resorts contribute to and support the development of infrastructure for education, healthcare, business training and mentorship and other social needs with 4.05 as its weighted mean. Generally, the respondents strongly agree with regard to their contributions in terms of economic aspects with 4.40 overall weighted mean.

Contrary to the result of the study, Marasigan and Borbon (2021) found out that with regard to the number of years of operation, majority or 60 percent of the resorts have been operating for 5 to 10 years while 11 to 15 years and 16 years and above got both two and 20 percent.

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
1. Contributes to higher income and standard of living	4.19	A
2. Resort owners accelerate structural change by replacing established, sclerotic/weak firms	4.24	SA
3. Increases the assets of the owner	4.48	SA
4. Increases the capacity of employees to avail goods and services	4.24	SA
5. Contributes to and supports the development of infrastructure for education, healthcare, business training and mentorship and other social needs	4.05	A
6. Contributes through payment of taxes to government revenue which consequently facilitates development	4.71	SA
7. Provides job opportunities in the short and long term for locals	4.57	SA
8. Generation of other local economies like sari-sari stores and restaurants	4.29	SA
9. Encourage competition from other entrepreneurs which challenges existing firms to become more competitive	4.43	SA
10. Promotes local tourism and attract more tourists (local and foreign) to visit the area	4.81	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	4.40	SA

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 – Strongly Agree (SA); 3.40 – 4.19 – Agree (A); 2.60 – 3.39 – Neutral (N); 1.80 – 2.59 – Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.79 – Strongly Disagree (SD)

The table implies that resort business greatly helps the local economy in terms of promoting and attracting local and foreign tourist to visit the area. The growing numbers of resorts in the province creates demand for specific goods and specialized services, including transport, accommodation, travel, and supporting services to meet the needs of niche and emerging travel markets such as adventure, health and wellness, creative and sports tourism. The result indicates that resort owners promote the development of activities and attractions, infrastructure and equipment to accommodate and attract domestic and international visitors.

The second highest contributions of resort owners in economic aspects is the generation of government revenue through payment of taxes which consequently facilitates development. It can be inferred from the result that resort owners are significant contributors to the local economic growth and development. They are required to pay taxes and comply with needed legal requirements among others in the local community.

One of the highest contributions of resort owners in economic aspects is providing jobs in the short and long term for the locals. Based on the interview with respondents, they employ locals as resort employees not only because they knew the area well, affordable salaries and wages they can offer but also to help increase employment in the province as a way of giving back to the community.

Contrarily, making contributions to and providing support for the establishment of infrastructure for healthcare, business mentoring and training, and other social requirements is at the lowest level. It suggests that because the resort owners have minimal resources and are still starting out in the industry, they have not yet decided to offer extension services to the local population. However, there are other methods for a business to get engaged

without investing a lot of money, from volunteering for community projects to helping locals who want to launch a business. Any company can participate, but how it contributes will largely depend on its circumstances. Also, on the respondents' perspective, they were not aware of how the government utilizes the taxes being paid by businesses particularly on infrastructure development projects and activities.

In terms of economic factors, it makes up the second-smallest contribution to rising income and living standards. The fact that the resorts have only been open for five years or less demonstrates how little they can do to raise living standards and provide better incomes due to their modest size. The majority of small enterprises need many years to succeed. It demonstrates that years, not months, are needed to create successful small businesses.

Environmental Aspects. Table 7 shows the impact and environmental contribution of resorts in Camarines Norte. Respondents strongly agreed that resorts create more hand washing and toilet flushing facilities which are functional at all times with 4.71 weighted mean; enhances other eco-friendly initiatives such providing trash bins with labels for proper segregation and wastes disposal 4.67 weighted mean; and spreads ecological knowledge thru posters, flyers, social media, etc. with 4.43 weighted mean; strengthens the implementation Clean As You Go (CLAYGO) with 4.38 weighted mean.

On the other hand, resorts owners agree that investing in technologies to decrease wastage like automated showers, VRF air conditioning units and other resort equipment with 3.86 weighted mean; decreases energy consumption by using solar panels with 3.29 weighted mean. Generally, the respondents strongly agree with regard to their contributions in terms of environmental aspects with 4.20 overall weighted mean.

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
1. Resorts improve the scenic spots of the area making them more inviting for other residents without destroying natural landscapes	4.33	SA
2. Acquires new technologies in cleaning and disinfecting all the general facilities	4.24	SA
3. Building more eco-lodges by using eco-friendly materials that blend in the natural environment	4.05	A
4. Investing in technologies to decrease wastage like automated showers, VRF air conditioning units and other resort equipment	3.86	A
5. Decreases energy consumption by using solar panels	3.29	A
6. Enhances other eco-friendly initiatives such providing trash bins with labels for proper segregation and wastes disposal	4.67	SA
7. Strengthens the implementation of CLAYGO (Clean As You Go)	4.38	SA
8. Resorts create more handwashing and toilet flushing facilities which are functional at all times	4.71	SA
9. Spreads ecological knowledge thru posters, fliers, social media, etc.	4.43	SA
10. Advocates organic farming and planting	4.05	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	4.20	SA

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 – Strongly Agree (SA); 3.40 – 4.19 – Agree (A); 2.60 – 3.39 – Neutral (N); 1.80 – 2.59 – Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.79 – Strongly Disagree (SD)

The table shows that resorts owners strongly agree that resort establishments create more hand washing and toilet flushing facilities which are functional at all times as its primary contribution in terms of environmental aspects. Given that tourists are picky, one of their top priorities when choosing a hotel is a resort with all the amenities, like comfortable rooms that are tidy and secure. Because the provincial tourism must adhere to the conditions listed on the Department of Tourism (DOT) checklist before issuing an accreditation certificate to the resort facilities, it means that the aforementioned environmental contributions take on the greatest priority.

The second highest contribution is enhancing other eco-friendly initiatives such providing trash bins with labels for proper segregation and wastes disposal. Waste disposal begins with good waste management, which involves reducing garbage production, recycling appropriate waste, and reusing surplus materials. It only indicates that resort owners are conscious of their duty to provide hygienic facilities and to uphold order in terms of cleanliness and correct trash disposal. This complies with local laws for garbage disposal because it is necessary to preserve the environment while reaping its benefits. As additional support to the findings, the Republic Act No. 9003, otherwise known as the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000, were being implemented and monitored in the province of Camarines Norte.

The second lowest contribution in terms of environmental aspects is resort operators agree that they need to invest in technologies to decrease wastage like automated showers, VRF air conditioning units and other resort equipment. Given that they are new and are in operations for five years and below based on the result of Table 5, they have no investments yet for infrastructure development which are costly and expensive. They are still under the developing stage and they prioritize the basic amenities needed for resorts to be fully operational.

The lowest contribution is decreasing energy consumption by using solar panels. It implies that resort

owners are now considering this to decrease wastage of resources as well as energy consumption in an economically friendly way; however, not all of them are able to do so as it is costly on their part as it needs intensive investment. Additionally, on the resort owners' point of view, there is no need yet for acquiring solar panels since fewer customers avail overnight packages which highly affect the return on investment. During these times, majority of customers prefer daily packages with guests commonly involving families, friends and company or office outings.

Social Aspects. Table 8 shows the extent on social aspects contributions of resort owners in the province of Camarines Norte. The respondents strongly agreed that resorts promote cultural identity of the local community in positive ways such as adapting to tourism inclined businesses, with 4.29 weighted mean; promotes social interactions among residents and tourists, with 4.29 weighted mean; and resorts provide higher opportunity for leisure, with 4.24 weighted mean.

On the other hand, the respondents also agree that resorts seek to satisfy client needs and improve livelihood in the community, with 4.14 weighted mean; provides recreational facilities for residents as well as tourists, with 4.14 weighted mean; raised the standard-of-living further by providing a wider range of services and amenities in the local area, with 4.10 weighted mean; provides better social services in the forms of outreach programs such as scholarship grants and respond to community needs, with 4.0 weighted mean; contributes to the improvement of the situation for women and children thru actively supporting community civic organizations and in giving back to the charitable groups in the locality, with 4.0 weighted mean; involves in sponsorships of tournaments and events in the localities, with 3.57 weighted mean; and that resorts preservation of heritage, culture and local customs, with 4.24 weighted mean. Generally, the respondents agree with regard to their contributions in terms of social aspects with 4.09 overall weighted mean.

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
1. Promotes cultural identity of the local community in positive ways such as adapting to tourism inclined businesses	4.29	SA
2. Promotes social interactions among residents and tourists	4.29	SA
3. Seeks to satisfy client needs and improve livelihood in the community	4.14	A
4. Provides recreational facilities for residents as well as tourists	4.14	A
5. Provides better social services in the forms of outreach programs such as scholarship grants and respond to community needs	4.00	A
6. Contributes to the improvement of the situation for women and children thru actively supporting community civic organizations and in giving back to the charitable groups in the locality	4.00	A
7. Raises the standard-of-living further by providing a wider range of services and amenities in the local area	4.10	A
8. Involves in sponsorships of tournaments and events in the localities	3.57	A
9. Preservation of heritage, culture and local customs	4.10	A
10. Higher opportunity for leisure	4.24	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	4.09	Agree

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 – Strongly Agree (SA); 3.40 – 4.19 – Agree (A); 2.60 – 3.39 – Neutral (N); 1.80 – 2.59 – Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.79 – Strongly Disagree (SD)

The table shows that resort owners strongly agree that their primary contributions in terms of social aspects are promoting cultural identity of the local community in positive ways such as adapting to tourism inclined businesses and promoting social interactions among residents and tourists. The inclusion of some local dishes in the menu; allowing the locals to sell their own products in the area; inclusion of local producers of delicacies and other locally made products to their directory or partnering them. Also, the resort owners also promote cultural identity by promoting cultural activities such as fiesta and posting such events on their Facebook pages highlighting their participation are some of their ways of promoting cultural identity. It clearly shows that resort operators are strongly considering the cultural aspect of the locality and transforming it as a good marketing tool that will not only promote the business but the locality itself.

The second lowest contribution of resort owners in terms of social aspects is providing better social services in the forms of outreach programs such as scholarship grants and respond to community needs, and contributes to the improvement of the situation for women and children thru actively supporting community civic organizations and in giving back to the charitable groups in the locality. It implies that as of this moment, majority of them are not capable extend services to the community.

The least contribution of resort owners in terms of social aspects is involvement in sponsorships of tournaments and events in the localities. It implies that majority of the resort owners were not capable to get involved in the aforementioned social activities because most of them are newly established or existing for 5 years and below as result of number of years in operation in Table 5. These resorts are not yet considered reaching the stability or maturity period and majority of them also experienced shortage of funds due to increasing expenses on utilities like electricity and water.

C. Significant Relationship between the Profile of the Resort Owners and the Extent of Agreement on their Contributions

Table 12 shows the result of the test for significant relationship between the profile of the resort owners and the extent of agreement on their contributions. Somers' delta (*d*) Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the relationship which may exist between the extent of agreement on the contributions of the resort owners and their profile as to age, educational attainment, number of employees, and number of years in business while Rank Biserial Correlation (*r_{rb}*) was used to determine the relationship as to civil status profile. The table shows the result tested 15% level of significance.

Profile	Extent of Agreement on the Contribution					
	Economic Aspects		Environmental Aspects		Social Aspects	
	Test Statistics	p value	Test Statistics	p value	Test Statistics	p value
Age	0.162	0.225	0.257	0.13	0.184	0.31
Civil Status	0.516*	0.017	0.363	0.105	0.084	0.717
Educational Attainment	0.127	0.403	0.216	0.362	0.029	0.912
Number of Employees	0.154	0.212	-0.462	0.145	-0.359	0.154
Number of Years in Business	-0.09	0.555	0.131	0.533	-0.007	0.969

The table shows a statistically significant moderate positive relationship at between civil status profile and extent of agreement on the economic contributions of the resort owners (*r_{rb}* = 0.516, *p* = 0.017). This result suggests relationship between civil status profile of the resort owners and their perceived economic contributions. Based on the result, respondents who are married and widowed signified their strong agreement on their economic contributions as resort owners. It implies that for many couples, starting business together feels exciting, ambitious, and even more romantic. Couples working together on a business can't be afraid of difficult conversations. According to the interview, even husband and wife have a different business outlooks, their knowledge of one another meant that it was easier and more intuitive to make decisions than with business associates. However, no significant relationship exists along environmental and social aspects. This shows that despite of the resort owners' profile, they are aware in the

implementation of environmental policies and regulations. They give more emphasis in preserving the monuments, heritage structures which are around their vicinity. They also have great appreciation in the provision of better leisure facilities, organizing frequent social events and thus a better lifestyle for the local people.

The table also shows no significant relationship between the age, educational attainment, number of employees, and number or years in business profile and extent of agreement on the economic contributions of the resort owners. The Somer's coefficient values in Table 9 with *p* values greater than 0.05 suggest an acceptance of the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship or association between the profile of the respondents and the extent of agreement on the economic contributions of the resort owners. It simply implies that resort owners, regardless of their age, number of employees, years in

business, or degree of education, can help the province's economy expand by creating jobs for residents and supporting other local businesses like running retail or sari-sari stores.

D. Challenges Encountered by Resort Owners in terms of Marketing, Operations Management and Human Resource Management

Challenges Encountered in terms of Marketing. Table 10 shows the main challenges encountered by resort owners in their operation in terms of their marketing. Data shows that there are moderate problems, particularly on lack of time and resources, with 2.62 weighted mean; difficulty in maintaining ads content, with 2.81; no clear strategy in promoting the resorts, with 2.52 weighted mean; high

accommodation rates, with 2.48 weighted mean; inability to adapt new trends, with 2.57 weighted mean; Inability to identify customer's preferences, with 2.62 weighted mean; lack of customers during off-peak season, with 3.10 weighted mean; customer complaints, with 2.05 weighted mean; and challenge in selecting an appropriate marketing platform with 2.57 weighted mean.

Above all, there is one indicator that were considered as a serious problem of these resort owners and this is the stiff competition, with a weighted mean of 3.43, this is seen between and among other resorts, that are not accredited by the provincial tourism office and other offices. Generally, the overall weighted mean is 2.68 which is interpreted as moderate problem.

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
1. Stiff competition	3.43	SP
2. Lack of time and resources	2.62	MoP
3. Difficulty in maintaining ads content	2.81	MoP
4. No clear strategy in promoting the resorts	2.52	MoP
5. High accommodation rates	2.48	MiP
6. Inability to adapt new trends	2.57	MoP
7. Inability to identify customer's preferences	2.62	MoP
8. Lack of customers during off-peak season	3.10	MoP
9. Customer complaints	2.05	MiP
10. Challenge in selecting an appropriate marketing platform	2.57	MoP
Overall Weighted Mean	2.68	MoP

Legend: 3.24 – 4.00 – Serious Problem (SP); 2.50 – 3.23 – Moderate Problem (MoP); 1.75 – 2.49 – Minor Problem (MiP); and 1.00 – 1.74 – Not at all a Problem (NP)

The table above shows that the serious problems that resort business have to face an on top of the list is the stiff competition. The result clearly indicates that the resort industry has grown to be appealing, and more investors are now ready to risk investing in this type of firm. Many landowners nowadays have converted their properties into resorts since they can see that the tourism industry is lucrative. In addition, more and more individuals are able to travel because to ongoing road development and advancements in transportation technology. Some people seized the chance and entered the resort industry.

Another serious problem that respondents encounter is the lack of customers during off-peak season. Off-seasons are primarily caused by the country's climate, particularly during the rainy season, when there are few to no visitors since they will not take advantage of the amenities, the vistas, or the safety risk. According to the interviews, they give promotions like discounts and freebies to draw in clients or visitors in order to at least increase sales during off-peak seasons.

The result also shows some minor problems that arise from time to time such as customer complaints. As observed during the conduct of the study, there were no feedback mechanisms currently being employed by the resort owners. Issues such as these usually arise especially during peak seasons wherein, they cater to many customers at a time. There will always be a possibility of unhappy or dissatisfied

customer if they were not able to meet their demands on time.

The cost or high lodging rates are an additional minor issue. This cannot be avoided, especially since opening a resort requires a significant amount of resources to construct and market the facilities. Because they are new to the business and have been operating for less than five years, they will incur large startup costs that cannot be covered by a meager return on investment. Instead, they will have to pass along these costs to guests by raising resort rates. They have to work and earn money in order to maintain the amenities at the resort.

Challenges Encountered in terms of Operations Management. Table 11 shows the main challenges encountered by resorts owners in Camarines Norte. The moderate problems they were encountering were continued technological changes and innovations and implementation of government policies on resorts, with 2.90 weighted mean; followed by lack of refreshing events and entertainment, with 2.76 weighted mean.

It is also evident that resorts owners were experiencing minor problems such as mishandled reservations and double bookings, with 2.05 weighted mean and there is one serious problem that these resorts are experiencing, which is the high cost of operations, with a weighted mean of 3.52. Generally, the overall weighted mean is 2.67 which is interpreted as moderate problem.

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
1. Challenge in cash flow and financial management	2.57	MoP
2. High cost of operations	3.52	SP
3. Frequent interruptions and maintenance calls	2.48	MiP
4. Lack of refreshing events and entertainment	2.76	MoP
5. No proper transportation facility	2.57	MoP
6. Lack of planning	2.48	MiP
7. Continued technological changes and innovations	2.90	MoP
8. Mishandled reservations and double bookings	2.05	MiP
9. Implementation of government policies on resorts	2.90	MoP
10. Resort safety and security risks	2.48	MiP
Overall Weighted Mean	2.67	MoP

Legend: 3.24 – 4.00 – Serious Problem (SP); 2.50 – 3.23 – Moderate Problem (MoP); 1.75 – 2.49 – Minor Problem (MiP); and 1.00 – 1.74 – Not at all a Problem (NP)

The table shows the different challenges in operations and management. On top of the list is the high cost of operations. This refers to the expenses that are required to keep the resort business running, such as utility costs, salaries and wages, repairs and maintenance costs, promotional expenses, costs of raw materials, and commissions. These expenses are found within all operating departments, which include rooms, sales and marketing, and property operations.

The continued technological changes and innovations and implementation of government policies on resorts as both can be considered as second to the highest encountered challenges by resort owners in term of operations management, interpreted moderate problem that resort owners need to face and solve. Given that the resort locations were at far-flung areas in the locality, they need to provide internet connectivity which are stable, accommodations which are quality and of standards given the many choices to choose from and while doing these, they also need to satisfy the government regulations in operating a resort particularly addressing environmental problems that may be brought by resort in the area.

Mishandled reservations and double bookings as a result of resort staff members' lack of training and workshops rank as the lowest minor issue depending on the outcome. It suggests that resort owners have a set booking and reservation system in place. It aids resort owners in

enhancing how their company runs and works toward the ultimate objectives of improved efficiency and the guest experience.

Also, the result shows another minor problem such as challenge in cash flow and financial management, and no proper transportation facility. Cash flow is attributed to inaccurate cost accounting and poor margins. Also, heavy debt burdens or predatory loans are bled dry making payments, leaving no cash available for growth. The inconsistent arrival of customers contributed to challenges in operations because if there's no customers meaning no income that will keep the resort running.

Challenges Encountered in terms of Human Resource Management. Table 12 shows the main challenges encountered by resort owners in Camarines Norte in terms of human resource management. Majority of the resorts revealed that they are having minor problems in the following: staff turn-over and skilled labour shortage, both with a weighted mean of 2.48, while personal conflict between employees, with 2.52 weighted mean stood out to be a moderate problem. Personal conflict between employees is considered lowest minor problem with 1.86 weighted mean and no proper delegation of work placed as the second lowest minor problem among the challenges encountered with 1.95 weighted mean. Generally, the overall weighted mean is 2.28 which is interpreted as minor problem.

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
1. Skilled labor shortage	2.48	MiP
2. Lack of human resource plan	2.33	MiP
3. Non-existent of employee's handbook	2.24	MiP
4. Lack of employee's professional trainings and seminars	2.43	MiP
5. Miscommunication between teams	2.24	MiP
6. No proper delegation of works	1.95	MiP
7. Retaining and attracting employees	2.52	MoP
8. Staff turn-over	2.48	MiP
9. Irregular shift work or working longer weekly hours	2.29	MiP
10. Personal conflict between employees	1.86	MiP
Overall Weighted Mean	2.28	MiP

Legend: 3.24 – 4.00 – Serious Problem (SP); 2.50 – 3.23 – Moderate Problem (MoP); 1.75 – 2.49 – Minor Problem (MiP); and 1.00 – 1.74 – Not at all a Problem (NP)

The table shows the challenges in human resource management that resort businesses need to face. Staff turnover and hiring skilled laborers/employees are at the top of the list. Finding skilled workers can be challenging, particularly given the nature of the industry and the fact that no one invests in the training and professional development of those who enter this line of work. Operators must develop their own staff members well and give them the skills they need to accomplish their jobs correctly. Employee turnover is a big issue as well since workers want security in the pay they will receive in exchange for their services. Mistreating them sometimes or they feel that they are not properly paid or they find other offers of a better income – then one minute – that worker will be gone. So having a loyal employee in this kind of business venture is a rare find especially if the organization cannot properly pay their employees or the business having a hard time staying afloat.

No proper delegation of works is the second minor problem being encountered in terms of human resource management. Since the employees are small in number and there are no written duties and responsibilities given by the resort owners, they were performing based on what is assigned to them and they can do other tasks as need arises and multi-task depending on the situation. It have shown that multitasking actually damages productivity. However, despite many studies demonstrating this kind of approach

can boost productivity. They perceived this as minor problem as the resort tasks are manageable.

The least problem is personal conflict with employees. It implies that the employees of resorts considering their small number have harmonious work relationships among each other. It shows that employees who prioritize relationships with their co-employees and lead from a place of positivity and kindness simply do better, and company culture has a bigger influence on employee well-being than salary and benefits. Based on the interview with resort owners, the employees treat each and every one as equals and they develop friendships and camaraderie in their workplace.

E. Significant Relationship between the Profile and the Challenges Encountered by Resort Owners

The result of the test for significant relationship between the profile of the resort owners and the challenges encountered by resort owners in its operations. Somers’ Delta Correlation Coefficient (*d*) was used to determine the relationship that may exist between the perceived challenges of the resort owners and their profile as to age, educational attainment, number of employees, and number of years in business while Rank Biserial Correlation (r_{rb}) was used to determine the relationship as to civil status profile. Table 13 shows the result tested at 5 percent level of significance.

Profile	Challenges Encountered by Resort Owners					
	Marketing		Operations Management		Human Resource Management	
	Test Statistics	p value	Test Statistics	p value	Test Statistics	p value
Age	0.179	0.333	0.201	0.226	0.218	0.134
Civil Status	0.533*	0.013	0.411	0.064	0.257	0.261
Educational Attainment	-0.265	0.407	-0.01	0.97	-0.118	0.595
Number of Employees	0.641	0.159	0.256	0.193	0.205	0.522
Number of Years in Business	0.028	0.882	0.090	0.596	0.186	0.297

*Significant @ 0.05 level of significance

The table shows a statistically significant moderate positive relationship at between civil status profile and perceived challenges of the resort owners ($r_{rb} = 0.533$, $p = 0.013$). This data suggests an association between civil status profile and the perceived challenges encountered as resort owners along marketing. However, no significant relationship exists along operations management and human resource management. Based on the result, respondents who are married and widowed identified marketing aspects their experienced challenges. As shown in Table 10, placed on top among the challenges encountered by resort owners is stiff competition, mostly seen between and among other resorts that are not accredited by the provincial tourism office. In this case, marketing their resort business is becoming a real challenge on the part of the resort owners. Also, the lack of customers during off-peak create enormous impact on their levels of revenue. Further, the obligations as family-oriented individuals, being typically Filipino makes

them balance both the demands of household work and as owners managing the resort businesses.

The table also shows no significant relationship between the age, educational attainment, number of employees, and number or years in business profile and extent of agreement on the economic contributions of the resort owners. The Somer’s coefficient values in Table 13 with p-values greater than 0.05 suggest an acceptance of the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship or association between the profile and the perceived challenges encountered as resort owners. It only means that business profiles are not related to the cause of the challenges experienced by the resort business. This challenges that they experienced are mainly caused of the results of their actual operations and marketing management.

F. Proposed Promotion and Management Plan to Strengthen the Resort Operations in the Province of Camarines Norte

Table 14 shows the proposed promotion and management plan to strengthen the resort operations in the province of Camarines Norte. The basis for the strategies and activities were the results of the low contributions of resort owners in terms of social, economic and environmental aspects. In addition, the main challenges being encountered by them need to be addressed and

prioritized to be able to maintain and sustain their competitiveness given the hyper competition in this type of industry.

The promotion of resorts in the Camarines Norte can help the people sustain their daily needs and have income through tourists visiting the place. To attract more tourists, the resort owners may come up with innovative measures to maintain repeat business.

Promotional Tools	Objectives	Promotional Strategies and Management Plans	Expected Outcome
Digital Advertising	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To communicate the products and services through online platform. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capitalize on viral marketing using internet advertising techniques in social media platforms to broadcast price reduction promotions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased online bookings Increase in customer awareness Positive return on sales
Direct Marketing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To provide customers with information relative to their needs and interests. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highlight special offers, exclusive deals and new products via email marketing. Make constant connections to key accounts (loyal individual clients and business organizations) using insert media strategies in sending marketing materials such as the catalogs and personalized items inserted into the communications. Provide regular updates and follow-ups with key clients using mobile marketing and maximize the power of this platform to perform customer relationship management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Builds relationships with new customers Test the appeal of product or service Provide customers with compelling content they can share with potential customers Increase sales
Sales Promotion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To develop favorable consumer experience with the product. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design creative contest to attract and encourage guests to make a purchase of the product and submit an entry to the contest and give guests a chance to win prizes in the form of cash incentives or even vacations. Capitalize on rebates program by creating value through point system for client's regular subscription of the products and services. Offer discounts and rebate program for extended stays or frequent visits. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Satisfied customers with the promotion and the overall product or service Attract new customers to avail the products and services Launch new product and increase trial Entice more resort customers during the lean months
Public Relations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To raise awareness of the business, build and manage the business' reputation and cultivate relationships with consumers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hosting of summer promotional events and special holiday events with the aid of the Department of Tourism, City Tourism Office and Municipal Tourism Office. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) through civic engagement in partnerships with LGUs, NGAs, and other agencies. Create strong visual identity such as recognizable logo, trade dress, signages, slogans, etc. to facilitate brand recognition to effectively promote market penetration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase the visibility and awareness of resort customers as regards to products and services Build beneficial relationships between an organization and the public communities, groups, and people it serves. Help raise your business' profile and improve your reputation
Customer Service Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To build personal relationships with customers, increase repeat business and promote word-of-mouth referrals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide a venue for customers to leave anonymous feedback and look for common denominators and work on creating customer connection ideas based on the results. Provide an interactive social media experience by being responsive to their queries via social media outlets. Provide customers with interaction that speaks to them as individuals to determine the specifics about their individual needs and preferences. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Build personal relationship with customers Attract more customers to avail the products and services Help the front desk receptionist to get immediate feedback about client objections or misunderstandings about marketing messages Increase sales

A resort's marketing is distinct from all other types of marketing. Before they even set foot on the resort's property, content, design, and pictures must enthrall both domestic and international tourists. Only resort-specific digital marketing techniques can make this happen. Although the global pandemic has negatively impacted resorts, this does not mean that resort operators should stop marketing until the sector has fully recovered. While their rivals hold back, they must control the top spots on social media and raise brand awareness. In other words, resorts still need to invest in digital marketing.

Another promotional tool which greatly promotes resort business is direct marketing. Print in the form of newspaper advertising, directory listings, magazine ads, and brochure distribution is widely used. Direct marketing with print media is quickly becoming a lost art in some sectors of the marketplace. With everything moving toward the Internet and instant-information sources, some businesses may not allocate enough of their advertising budget to more traditional mediums of lead generation or sales. Those in the resort industry has a unique opportunity to make their presence known in a very physical and real way with direct marketing.

Sales promotions are currently being offered as inducements to existing and prospective buyers or users of resort accommodation. Commonly used sales Promotional techniques may include discount, freebies, premium, bonus, bundle packs, contest, coupons, among others. Sales promotion techniques are those tools which are used to accelerate the sales of a particular product/service.

In the resort business sector, a fundamental part of creating visibility is public relations; resorts must rely on this branch of communications as a complimentary part of their marketing efforts. Having a clear strategy of the actions that resort will take to help strengthen the resort's brand through events and other promotional activities is key to setting the resort apart from the competition. Through public relations, resort owners can maintain a solid relationship with media outlets and guests throughout the year in order to ensure the year-round success of the resort business.

Lastly, a customer service strategy is a thorough plan to handle customer interactions. It provides resort owners a consistent customer experience throughout the customer journey. Improved customer experience results in a more loyal customer base. Loyal customers buy more often, spend more, and promote word-of-mouth referrals.

VIII. SUMAMRY, CONCLIUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study aimed to determine the contributions and challenges of resort owners in the province of Camarines Norte. It answered the following questions: 1) What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, civil status, educational attainment, number of employees, and number of years in business; 2) what are the contributions of resort owners in terms of economic, environmental, and social

aspects; 3) Is there a significant relationship between the profile and the challenges of resort owners; 4) What are the main challenges of resort owners encountered in the resorts operations in terms of marketing, operations management, and human resource management; 5) Is there a significant relationship between the profile and the challenges of resort owners encountered in resort operations; and 6) What promotion and management plan may be proposed to strengthen the resort operations in the province of Camarines Norte?

Descriptive-correlational method of research was employed in the study. The survey questionnaire was the primary research instrument used for data gathering. A total of 21 accredited resorts in the province of Camarines Norte identified by the Provincial Tourism Office were the study respondents.

Frequency count and percentage were used to evaluate the profile of the respondents such as age, number of employees, number of years in business and highest educational background. Weighted mean was used to determine the contributions resort owners on the economic, environmental, and social aspects together with the challenges in resort operations particularly in terms of marketing, operations management and human resource management. Variation statistics such as Somer's Delta Correlation Coefficient and Rank Biserial Correlation were also used to determine the significant relationship between the profile and their contributions will also be analyzed as well as the relationship between profile and the challenges of the resort owners.

A. Findings

- The age bracket of 35 to 44 has the highest percentage of 23.8 percent with a frequency of five. This is followed by the age brackets of 45 to 54, 55 to 64, and 65 and above, which has 19 percent and with a frequency of four. The age bracket of 35 to 34, on the other hand, has 14.3 percent or three respondents. Also, the youngest age bracket is 24 and below with the lowest percentage of 4.8 which is equivalent to one respondent. Majority of the respondents comprising of 14 which is equivalent to 66.7 percent were married. This is followed by the single respondents with a total of five which is equivalent to 23.8 percent. Lastly, the widowed respondents were two, equivalent to 9.5 percent. Majority of which are college graduates with 15 and equivalent to 71.4 per cent. Followed by college level which yielded 14.3 percent or three respondents. Last were the equal frequency of one for elementary level, masteral units, and doctoral diploma with 4.8 percent. It is evident that most of the resorts has ten and below number of employees, with 19 having an equivalent of 90.5 percent. This is followed by both 21 to 30 and 30 to 40 employees with one or 4.8 percent. The highest frequency is ten or 47.6 percent of the total population of the respondents. This is followed by 6 to 10 years and 11 to 15 years in the business, both with 23.8 percent, making them the second longest. Lastly is 16 to 20 years in business with one or 4.8 percent.

- Resort owners in Camarines Norte strongly agree that resorts contribute to the economic aspect of the province with a total weighted mean of 4.40. As the researchers find that resort business promotes local tourism and attract more tourists (local and foreign) to visit the area with a weighted mean of 4.81 as the highest result. While the resorts contribute to and support the development of infrastructure for education, healthcare, business training and mentorship and other social needs with 4.05 as its weighted mean. They also strongly agree that they are contributing on the environmental aspect of the province with an average weighted mean of 4.20. With the resorts create more hand washing and toilet flushing facilities which are functional at all times has the highest result with 4.71 weighted mean and the lowest result being resort business decreases energy consumption by using solar panels with a 3.29 weighted mean. As for contribution in terms of social aspects of the province with an average weighted mean of 4.09. Having both this contribution of resorts that promotes cultural identity of the local community in positive ways such as adapting to tourism inclined businesses and promotes social interactions among residents and tourists, both having the highest result of 4.29 weighted mean. While sponsorships of tournaments and events in the localities got the lowest result with 3.57 weighted mean.
- Significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the extent of agreement on the contributions of the resort owners which showed a statistically significant moderate positive relationship at between civil status profile and extent of agreement on the economic contributions of the resort owners ($r_{rb} = 0.516$, $p = 0.017$). However, it can be observed that the p-values are always greater than 0.05 along environmental and social aspects.
- The study revealed the challenges encountered by resort owners in their operation in terms of their marketing which they considered moderate problem with 2.68 weighted mean. The indicator that was considered as a serious problem of these resort owners and this is the stiff competition with a weighted mean of 3.43 has the highest result. While, customer complaints with 2.05 weighted mean have the lowest result. Also, resorts in Camarines Norte were experiencing problems and challenges in their operations management which they consider a moderate problem, with a weighted mean of 2.67. The highest result got a weighted mean of 3.52 specifically the high cost of operations. Having mishandled reservations and double bookings with 2.05 weighted mean got the lowest result. Another is the minor problem in their resort operations particularly on human resource management, this is seen on their average weighted mean which is equivalent to 2.28. One stood out to be a moderate problem and has the highest result, this is retaining and attracting employees having a 2.52 weighted mean. Being personal conflict between employees got the lowest score of 1.86 weighted mean.
- Significant relationship between the profile and the challenges of the resort owners encountered in resort operations showed a statistically significant moderate positive relationship at between civil status profile and perceived challenges of the resort owners ($r_{rb} = 0.533$, $p = 0.013$). However, it can be observed that the p-values are greater than 0.05 along operations management and human resource management.
- The proposed promotion and management plan to strengthen the resort operations in the province of Camarines Norte were crafted based on the results of the study. The basis for the strategies and activities were the results of the low contributions of resort owners in terms of social, economic and environmental aspects. In addition, the main challenges being encountered by them need to be addressed and prioritized to be able to maintain and sustain their competitiveness given the hyper competition in this type of industry.

B. Conclusions

Based on the mentioned findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

- Most of the resort owners were at the age range of 35 to 44, married, college graduate, with masteral units, with ten and below number of employees, and six to ten years in the business.
- Resort owners in Camarines Norte strongly agree that resorts contribute to the economic aspect of the province. Specifically, resort business promotes local tourism and attract more tourists (local and foreign) to visit the area has the highest result of contribution in terms of economic aspects while creation of more hand washing and toilet flushing facilities which are functional at all times has the highest result in terms of environmental aspects and lastly, in terms of social aspects, promoting cultural identity of the local community in positive ways such as adapting to tourism inclined businesses and promotes social interactions among residents and tourists.
- Generally, there is no significant relationship between the profile of the resort owners except for civil status and economic contributions. Thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected.
- The study also revealed moderate challenges encountered by resort owners in their operation in terms of their marketing is stiff competition and high cost of operations in terms of operations management, while minor problem in their resort operations particularly on retaining and attracting employees in terms of human resource management.
- Generally, there is no significant relationship between the profile and the perceived challenges of resort owners except for civil status and the perceived challenges of the resort owners. Thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected.
- The proposed promotion and management plan to strengthen the resort operations in the province of Camarines Norte were crafted based on the results of the study may be adopted by the resort owners.

C. Recommendations

From the findings and conclusions drawn from the study, the following suggestions were recommended:

- Resort owners may strengthen their resort operations through investing with equipped and skilled human resource to sustain their operations and stay competitive given the hyper competition existing not only locally but nationally.
- As far as contributions to the economy, environment and social aspects is concerned, resort owners may provide environmental advocacies and campaigns to attract local or foreign tourist to sustain local tourism contributions for it helps open other social and economic opportunities to the locality.
- The Provincial Tourism Office, together with other concerned offices, may work together to address these concerns. Resort owners may look for possible partnership outside the province to boost their marketing and connections with allied businesses as this will help them generate more income and more visitors. As for operations management, they may consider the impact of their operation in the social and economical aspect of the local residents, as well as the impact it will have on the environment.
- To address the various challenges that were encountered, the resort owners may craft or enhance their own promotional plan. They may also consider including in their marketing campaign the culture and the beauty of the locality where the business is located. Asking for assistance to the local tourism the place may also be done to fully understand the culture of the locality. Thus, challenges in marketing and operations may be augmented if these resort owners were given free trainings and seminars.
- The local government bodies of the locality may implement policies that will favor resort owners without risking the impact of it to the environment as well as to the local residents. Local authorities may help this business venture thru their tourism campaigns as well as keeping peace and order on this business establishments to make this visiting people or tourists feel safe and relaxed.
- The proposed promotion and management plan to strengthen the resort operations along resort businesses in the province of Camarines Norte may be presented to the resort owners for possible adoption.
- Future researchers may opt to conduct a similar study about the impact of the new normal in the tourism sector, its adjustments and challenges on adapting to the new normal.

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